

Learning spurious associations from mathematics textbooks: A replication and extension study

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Abstract

We investigated the distribution of rational number arithmetic problems in mathematics textbooks and examined whether this distribution may lead to biased patterns and associations when working with fractions and decimals. We report findings from two complementary studies. In Study 1, we analyzed the distribution of rational number arithmetic problems (i.e., fraction and decimal problems) in the fifth- and sixth-grade volumes of two widely used mathematics textbook series in the German-speaking region of Switzerland. In Study 2, we investigated the effects of these distributions on 105 sixth-grade Swiss primary school students. Replicating prior research, the results of Study 1 revealed nonrandom and unbalanced distributions between arithmetic operations and operand features in both decimal and fraction problems. Study 2 demonstrated that sixth graders are influenced by these distributions, suggesting a development of spurious associations between operations and operand features due to the unbalanced presentation of problems in their mathematics textbooks. Exploratory cluster analyses refine the general findings of Study 2 by indicating that only some students develop spurious associations. Our findings highlight the role of textbook problem distributions in shaping students' learning. We discuss the implications of textbook problem distributions and emphasize the need for balanced, systematic approaches in instructional materials to support accurate and comprehensive learning of rational number arithmetic.

Keywords

textbook analysis, fraction arithmetic, decimal arithmetic, rational numbers, spurious associations.

1. Introduction

Understanding rational numbers and conducting algorithmic operations with them is important. An adequate knowledge of rational numbers is crucial for learning more advanced mathematics (Booth and Newton, 2012; Booth et al., 2014) and for occupational success (Handel, 2016). Nevertheless, many students (Carpenter et al., 1980; Kloosterman, 2010; Siegler and Lortie-Forgues, 2015; Martin et al., 2007; Behr et al., 1984; Luculano and Butterworth, 2011) and even adults and some mathematics teachers (Hanson and Hogan, 2000; Ma, 1999) have limited knowledge of rational numbers. In this paper, we examine a specific early source of these difficulties by analyzing the distributions of rational number problems in primary school mathematics textbooks (Study 1) and by exploring whether students learn spurious associations from these distributions (Study 2).

Children's difficulties and their potential sources when dealing with rational numbers are under scientific scrutiny (e.g., Lortie-Forgues et al., 2015; Lortie-Forgues and Siegler, 2017; Van Hoof et al., 2017). While several studies identify the natural number bias — overgeneralizing natural number rules to rational numbers — as a key source of difficulty (Moss, 2005; Ni and Zhou, 2005; Vamvakoussi and Vosniadou, 2010), other studies suggest that children's mistakes in rational number arithmetic often stem from choosing incorrect solution strategies (Siegler and Pyke, 2013; Siegler et al., 2011). For example, equality of denominators increased children's performance in addition and subtraction problems with fractions (Siegler & Pyke, 2013), but decreased performance in multiplication and division problems. Although the standard fraction multiplication procedure does not depend on the equality of denominators, children misapplied the strategy which would be appropriate for fraction addition or subtraction to multiplication or division problems.

To explain children's general difficulties as well as specific patterns of correct and incorrect solutions, Braithwaite et al. (2017) hypothesized that children's choice of solution strategies is rather based on associative knowledge than on the (mis-)application of mathematical rules

or conceptual understanding. Furthermore, they assumed that these associations arise from the unbalanced and non-random distribution of arithmetic problems in mathematics textbooks. To test this assumption, Braithwaite et al. (2017) analyzed three U.S. mathematics textbooks. The results of their analyses showed remarkably non-random and unbalanced relationships between arithmetic operations and operand features. To simulate the impact of these relationships on children's learning, Braithwaite et al. (2017) created a computational model of fraction arithmetic learning and presented it with the problems from one of the textbook series. Interestingly, many aspects of children's fraction arithmetic performance could be simulated by this computational model. For example, the computational model predicted low accuracy for fraction division. Looking back into mathematics textbooks, Braithwaite et al. (2017) observed that fraction division problems were introduced later and appeared far less frequently than other fraction arithmetic problems. When their model faced division problems, strategies of addition, subtraction, and multiplication had been repeatedly reinforced. This strong reinforcement made it difficult for their model to select the correct division strategy, which was much less reinforced. These observations suggested a general hypothesis regarding children's rational number arithmetic performance: children learn associations from the distributions of problems features and operations that are present in their mathematics textbooks.

Braithwaite and Siegler (2018) provided empirical evidence regarding this hypothesis. They presented children with three tasks: one in which children generated operand pairs for a given arithmetic operation, one in which they generated the operation for given operands, and one in which they matched operations to pairs of operands from two provided sets. As expected, children's responses reflected the non-random characteristics and distributions of the fraction arithmetic problems they encountered in their mathematics textbooks. Children seem to learn spurious associations which can hinder mastery of fraction arithmetic (see also Ben-Zeev & Star, 2001; Chang, Koedinger, & Lovett, 2003).

The learning of spurious associations driven by distributions of textbook problems has been demonstrated for decimal problems, too. Tian, Braithwaite, and Siegler (2021) identified imbalanced distributions of decimal arithmetic problems in three U.S. mathematics textbook series to describe. Consistent with the results from Braithwaite and Siegler (2018) for fraction arithmetic, Tian et al. (2021) showed that these biased distributions influenced children's decimal arithmetic by increasing the likelihood of learning spurious associations between operand features and operations.

Taken together, prior research has shown that U.S. mathematics textbooks contain biased distributions of fraction and decimal arithmetic problems, from which students learn spurious associations that negatively affect their performance in rational number arithmetic (Braithwaite & Siegler, 2018; Tian et al., 2021). However, it is unclear whether these phenomena generalize to other educational contexts. Swiss primary textbooks differ in structure, sequencing, and problem distributions, so the presence and profile of such biases—and the potential associations students may learn from them—require investigation. More importantly, by replicating the studies conducted in the U.S. in Switzerland, we aim to test the associative learning hypothesis, which states that spurious associations arise from the patterns of problems in textbooks rather than reflecting universal, inherent characteristics of rational number arithmetic. In Study 1, we quantify the distributions of fraction and decimal problems in two widely used Swiss textbook series. In Study 2, we test whether Swiss sixth graders acquire spurious associations from their textbooks, using a diverse set of tasks that includes those employed by Braithwaite and Siegler (2018), as well as additional novel tasks.

The Present Studies

We conducted two complementary studies. In Study 1, we examined the distributions of fraction and decimal arithmetic problems in the fifth and sixth grade volumes of two widely used mathematics textbook series in the German-speaking part of Switzerland. To foreshadow, we observed a nonrandom and unbalanced distribution of problems between arithmetic operations and operand features for both decimal and fraction problems.

In Study 2, we conceptually replicated the studies of Braithwaite and Siegler (2018). That is, we assessed whether Swiss sixth graders learned associations between operand features and operations from rational arithmetic problems in their textbooks. Thus, this conceptual replication tests the associative learning hypothesis in a different curricular context (Switzerland). To this aim, we designed two tests: the Fraction-Test and the Decimal-Test. Each test comprised five tasks to assess how children associate arithmetic operations with operand types. These tasks were: (1) given an operation, children had to generate two operands, (2) given an operation and an operand, children had to provide one operand, (3) given a pair of operands, children had to provide an operation, (4) given two pairs of operands and an operation, children had to assign the operation to one of the pairs of operands, and (5) given a pair of operands and two operations, children had to assign the operands to an operation. Three of these tasks (1, 3, 4) resemble the tasks used by Braithwaite and Siegler (2018) and Tian et al. (2021). We added two tasks (2, 5) to gather more valid responses given that some of the tasks we adopted from the prior studies might lead to results that cannot be interpreted (for details see the description of tasks in Section 3). Importantly, by investigating both fractions and decimals, we extend Braithwaite and Siegler's (2018) approach beyond fractions and provide the first experimental assessment of spurious associations in decimal arithmetic—a study not addressed in Tian et al. (2021). Our general overarching hypothesis was that children's responses will reflect the patterns found in their textbooks (i.e. the associative learning hypothesis), combining specific operand features with specific operations.

In addition to designing two novel tasks, we employed a more nuanced statistical analysis compared to the ones used in previous studies. While Braithwaite and Siegler (2018) used t-tests and ANOVAs, and Tian et al. (2021) employed Chi-square tests of independence, we tested our expectations using Bayesian binomial regressions across the entire sample, allowing us to model probabilities directly and thus to check whether observed imbalances exceed random variation. Anticipating variability in children's performance, we also conducted exploratory cluster analyses to estimate whether observed effects were consistent

across the entire sample or driven by specific subgroups. These analyses provide first insights into the heterogeneity of students' responses.

2. Textbook Content Analyses (Study 1)

We analysed and coded all fraction and decimal arithmetic problems stated in numerical form (i.e., not as word problems) in the fifth and sixth grade volumes of the two most widely used primary school textbook series in the German-speaking part of Switzerland: (1) Schweizer Zahlenbuch [SZB] (Klett und Balmer Verlag, 2017, 2018) and (2) Mathematik Themenbuch [MTB] (Lehrmittelverlag Zürich, 2015, 2016). Our goal was to check whether Swiss mathematics textbook series may also reveal imbalances in problem frequencies, as reported by Braithwaite and Siegler (2018) and Tian et al. (2021) for U.S. textbooks.

To this aim, we used a series of Bayesian binomial regressions to analyse the proportion of problems per operation and operand types. In accordance with prior research, we expected that specific combinations of operations and operand types are more frequent than others in the textbooks. We analysed frequencies of arithmetic operations in fraction and decimal problems. For fractions, we examined the frequencies of arithmetic problems with operands including whole numbers and fractions, two fractions with equal denominators, and two fractions with unequal denominators. For decimals, we analyzed the frequencies of arithmetic problems with operand being whole numbers and decimals, two decimals with equal digits, and two decimals with unequal digits.

2.1. Methodology

A fraction arithmetic problem had to meet five criteria to be included in the content analysis: (1) all problems were stated in numerical form (i.e., not as word problems), (2) the problem had two operands, (3) at least one operand was a fraction, (4) neither operand was a mixed number (e.g., $1\frac{2}{3}$), and (5) the problem required learners to generate a fraction as a solution, regardless of whether they were asked to expand or reduce the result.

Note that fraction problems involving mixed numbers were excluded in Study 1. Braithwaite and Siegler (2018) treated mixed numbers as fractions, we decided against including them because such problems were extremely rare in the Swiss textbooks we analyzed.

Overall, 294 problems in the SZB and 577 problems in the MTB met these criteria. Similarly, a decimal arithmetic problem had to meet five criteria to be included in the content analyses: (1) all problems were stated in numerical form (i.e., not as word problems), (2) the problem had two operands, (3) at least one operand was a decimal, (4) the problems did not include units of measurement, and (5) the problem required learners to generate a decimal as a solution, and not an estimate. Overall, 538 tasks in the SZB and 766 problems in the MTB met these criteria.

For fraction problems, following the approach of Braithwaite and Siegler (2018), we classified the problems into three groups: arithmetic operation problems between (1) fractions with equal denominators (e.g., $1/3 \times 2/3$), (2) fractions with unequal denominators (e.g., $1/4 + 2/5$), and (3) a fraction and a natural number (e.g., $3 - 1/2$). Table 1 presents the proportions of fraction problems in percentages for each arithmetic operation in each textbook series.

Following the approach of Tian et al. (2021), we classified all decimal arithmetic problems stated in numerical form into three groups. Arithmetic operation problems between (1) decimals with equal number of decimal digits (e.g., $9.02 + 5.27$), (2) decimals with unequal number of decimal digits (e.g., $9.002 + 5.27$), and (3) a decimal and a natural number (e.g., $3 - 1.6$). Table 2 presents the proportions of decimal problems in percentages for each of the four arithmetic operations in each textbook series. For both fraction and decimal problems, we observed a similar pattern for addition and subtraction, on the one hand, and multiplication and division, on the other hand. Thus, following the approach from Tian et al. (2021), we combined addition/subtraction and multiplication/division problems for all further analyses (see Tables 1 & 2).

Table 1: Percentages of fraction problems classified by operand types and arithmetic operations in both analyzed textbooks (Schweizer Zahlenbuch [SZB]; Mathematik Themenbuch [MTB])

Operand types	Operations	
	+/-	×/÷
SZB		
Equal denominators	3	2
Unequal denominators	56	12
Fraction-natural number	1	26
MTB		
Equal denominators	5	0
Unequal denominators	23	2
Fraction-natural number	1	68

Table 2: Percentages of decimal problems classified by operand types and arithmetic operations in both analyzed textbooks (Schweizer Zahlenbuch [SZB]; Mathematik Themenbuch [MTB])

Operand types	Operations	
	+/-	×/÷
SZB		
Equal number of decimal digits	32	3
Unequal number of decimal digits	12	2
Decimal-natural number	14	37
MTB		
Equal number of decimal digits	34	0
Unequal number of decimal digits	16	2
Decimal-natural number	3	46

2.2. Statistical Analyses

We analyzed the proportions of problems in each textbook to assess whether the observed imbalances exceed what could plausibly arise from random variation in problem selection.

For each textbook, we aggregated counts by operation (+/-, ×/÷) and operand type (Equal

denominators, Unequal denominators, Natural number), and modelled, for each combination, the number of problems out of the book's total.

Analyses were implemented as Bayesian binomial regressions in R using the *brms* package (Bürkner, 2018). Operation was coded with one dummy variable ($\times/\div = 1$, $+/- = 0$) and operand type with two dummy variables (Dummy 1: Equal = 1, Unequal = 0, Natural = 0; Dummy 2: Equal = 0, Unequal = 1, Natural = 0).

Given that we wanted to investigate whether operation and operand type are associated (i.e., not independent), we focus on their interaction. To assess the global effect of the interaction, we compared a baseline model with only main effects of operation and operand type to a model including the interaction. We used normal priors (mean = 0, SD = 1.5) for intercepts and coefficients, ran 4 chains with 5,000 iterations (1,000 warm-up), and compared models via LOO cross-validation ($\Delta\text{elpd}_{\text{loo}}$; Vehtari, Gelman, & Gabry, 2017). A better-fitting interaction model indicates dependence between operation and operand type, i.e., imbalances in the number of problems per operation within operand type (or vice versa). To probe the interaction, we ran pairwise comparisons using *bayestestR* (Makowski, Ben-Shachar, & Lüdtke, 2019), comparing \times/\div vs $+/-$ within each operand type.

For each comparison, we report the Probability of Direction (PD) and the percentage of the posterior that falls within the Region of Practical Equivalence (ROPE). On the one hand, the PD is an index of effect existence. It varies from 50 - 100%, reflects the proportion of the posterior distribution that has the same sign as the median, and is numerically similar to the frequentist p -value (e.g., a PD of 97.5% corresponds to a two-sided p -value of 0.05). Higher values therefore indicate higher certainty that an effect exists. On the other hand, we used the ROPE to compute the importance or "significance" of these effects. The ROPE specifies an explicit "null" region of values that are considered negligible. In the present study, we used a ROPE range of a small effect size, which in logistic models corresponds to a range from -.18 and 0.18 (Cohen, 1988). We then performed an equivalence test on the full

posterior: if less than 2.5% of the posterior lay within the ROPE, we considered the effect as non-negligible, i.e. “significant” (Makowski, Ben-Shachar, Chen, & Lüdtke, 2019).

For example, suppose a contrast (\times/\div vs $+/-$ within unequal denominators) has a posterior median of 0.13 with an 89% CI [0.04, 0.22]. The PD is 98.46%, i.e., 98.46% of the posterior is > 0 , indicating that there is high certainty that a positive effect exists. However, 5.58% of the posterior falls inside the ROPE from $-.18$ to $.18$, so the effect is not considered as “significant”, since it cannot be reliably distinguished from a small effect.

2.3. Results

The results of the textbooks analyses for fraction problems are presented in Figure 1a. In SZB, the interaction model fitted the data better than the baseline model ($\Delta\text{elpd}_{100} = -175.3$, $\Delta\text{SE} = 62.8$). For the operand type equal denominators, the contrast of $+/-$ vs. \times/\div had a 76.31% probability of being positive (Median = 0.008, 89% CI [-0.011, 0.028] and cannot be considered significant [22.36% in ROPE]); for the operand type unequal denominators, the contrast of $+/-$ vs. \times/\div had a 100% probability of being positive (Median = 0.426, 89% CI [0.372, 0.480] and is considered significant [0.00% in ROPE]); and for the operand type fraction-natural number, the contrast of $+/-$ vs. \times/\div had a 100% probability of being negative (Median = -0.216, 89% CI [-0.255, -0.174] and is considered significant [0.00% in ROPE]).

In MTB, the interaction model provided better model fit than the baseline model ($\Delta\text{elpd}_{100} = -498.5$, $\Delta\text{SE} = 115.6$), too. For the operand type equal denominators, the contrast of $+/-$ vs. \times/\div had a 100% probability of being positive (Median = 0.04, 89% CI [0.025, 0.055] and is considered significant [0.00% in ROPE]); for the operand type unequal denominators, the contrast of $+/-$ vs. \times/\div had a 100% probability of being positive (Median = 0.194, 89% CI [0.166, 0.224] and is considered significant [0.00% in ROPE]); and for the operand type fraction-natural number, the contrast of $+/-$ vs. \times/\div had a 100% probability of being negative (Median = -0.636, 89% CI [-0.668, -0.602] and is considered significant [0.00% in ROPE]).

Thus, there are clearly nonrandom and unbalanced relations between arithmetic operations and features of operands in the textbooks, however, slightly different from the results presented by Braithwaite and Siegler (2018). Compared to U.S. textbooks, which included addition and subtraction problems with equal- and unequal-denominator fractions at roughly similar rates, Swiss textbooks show a striking imbalance: addition and subtraction problems overwhelmingly involve unequal denominators, while equal-denominator cases are rare.

The results of the textbooks analyses for decimal problems are presented in Figure 1b. In SZB, the interaction model provided a better fit than the baseline model ($\Delta\text{elpd}_{\text{loo}} = -237.4$, $\Delta\text{SE} = 57.1$). For the operand type equal number of decimal digits, the contrast of $+/-$ vs. \times/\div had a 100% probability of being positive (Median = 0.289, 89% CI [0.256, 0.323]) and is considered significant [0.00% in ROPE]; for the operand type unequal number of decimal digits, the contrast of $+/-$ vs. \times/\div had a 100% probability of being positive (Median = 0.0988, 89% CI [0.076, 0.123]) and is considered significant [0.00% in ROPE]; and for the operand type decimal-natural number, the contrast of $+/-$ vs. \times/\div had a 100% probability of being negative (Median = -0.2168, 89% CI [-0.258, -0.177]) and is considered significant [0.00% in ROPE]. In MTB, the interaction model fitted the data better than the baseline model ($\Delta\text{elpd}_{\text{loo}} = -686.1$, $\Delta\text{SE} = 139.6$), too. For the operand type equal number of decimal digits, the contrast of $+/-$ vs. \times/\div had a 100% probability of being negative (Median = 0.332, 89% CI [0.306, 0.360]) and is considered significant [0.00% in ROPE]; for the operand type unequal number of decimal digits, the contrast of $+/-$ vs. \times/\div had a 100% probability of being positive (Median = 0.154, 89% CI [0.133, 0.175]) and is considered significant [0.00% in ROPE]; and for the operand type decimal-natural number, the contrast of $+/-$ vs. \times/\div had a 100% probability of being positive (Median = -0.405, 89% CI [-0.435, -0.374]) and is considered significant [0.00% in ROPE].

A comparison of decimal problems in Swiss versus U.S. textbooks analysed by Tian et al. (2021) reveals important differences. In Swiss textbooks, addition and subtraction of decimals were overwhelmingly presented with equal numbers of decimal digits, while

multiplication and division problems with two decimals (with equal or unequal numbers of decimal digits) were rare. By contrast, multiplication and division problems were much more common in the U.S. textbooks, involving not only two-decimal problems but also, and more frequently, combinations of decimals with whole numbers.

(a) Distribution of fraction problems in percentages among the three groups of problems in SZB and MTB and contrasted for +/- vs. x/÷

(b) Distribution of decimal problems in percentages among the three groups of problems in SZB and MTB and contrasted for +/- vs. x/÷

Figure 1: Distribution of fraction and decimal problems presented by groups of problems and textbooks contrasted for +/- vs. x/÷. Estimated median values are depicted as black lines and 89% credible intervals as error bars. Effects considered to be significant are highlighted by asterisks.

The content analysis reveals clear, nonrandom relations between arithmetic operations and operand types in the most widely used Swiss German primary school textbooks. Nonrandom relations, and thus a nonrandom distribution of problems was found for both fraction and decimal arithmetic problems, potentially leading children to learn spurious associations.

These patterns largely resemble, but differ also in part from those observed in U.S. textbooks, analyzed by Braithwaite and Siegler (2018) and Tian et al. (2021). Most notably (and to be explicitly tested in Study 2), in Swiss textbooks, children encounter +/- problems involving fractions with unequal denominators more frequently than those involving equal denominators. In contrast, U.S. textbooks present these two types of in roughly equal proportions. In Study 2, we test whether children have indeed learned spurious associations and whether these associations reflect the unbalanced, nonrandom distribution of problems identified in Swiss textbooks, thereby providing evidence in support of the associative learning hypothesis.

3. Assessing learning associations between operand features and operations (Study 2)

Study 1 indicated that Swiss children are presented with nonrandom and unbalanced distributions of fraction and decimal problems in their textbooks. The purpose of Study 2 is to test the overarching hypothesis that Swiss children would learn spurious associations between operand features and operations from these distributions. To this aim, six graders answered two tests: a Fraction-Test and a Decimal-Test. Both tests comprised different kinds of tasks. Below, in the Materials section, we describe the different kinds of tasks and present specific hypotheses for each task.

3.1. Methodology

3.1.1. Sample

Participants were 105 6th graders from 5 classes in 3 schools in the German-speaking part of Switzerland (ages from 10-12, 48.5% girls, 51.5% boys). They primarily learned rational number arithmetic using one of the two textbooks analyzed in Study 1 (i.e., Schweizer

Zahlenbuch [SZB], Klett und Balmer Verlag, 2018, or Mathematik Themenbuch [MZB], Lehrmittelverlag Zürich, 2016).

3.1.2. Materials

We designed two tests: a Fraction-Test and a Decimal-Test. Each test comprised five tasks: (1) generate-operands, (2) generate-operand, (3) choose-operation, (4) choosing an operand pair for a given operation, and (5) choosing an operation for given operands. Examples of trials for each task, our specific predictions and an overview of the results for both tests are presented in Tables 3 (Fraction-Test) and 4 (Decimal-Test). Recall that, tasks 1, 3, and 4 from the Fraction-Test are like those used by Braithwaite and Siegler (2018). To ensure more interpretable responses, we added two additional tasks (tasks 2 and 5), expanding our dataset with response formats that enforce valid answers. This approach was motivated by the structure of tasks 1 and 5. A detailed explanation of the design and purpose of these additional tasks is provided in the task description below.

Task 1: Generate-operands. Children completed eight trials per test, presented in the order $+$, $-$, \times , \div . Each trial showed two empty boxes with an operation in between, and children were instructed to fill the boxes with numbers that typically fit the operation. They were instructed to use two fractions or a fraction and a natural number, but not two natural numbers. For the Decimal-Test, children were instructed to use two decimals or a decimal and a natural number, but not two natural numbers.

Based on the distribution of problems in the Swiss textbooks, we made the following predictions. In the Fraction-Test, we expected children to primarily produce two fractions with unequal denominators for addition and subtraction and a fraction together with a natural number for multiplication and division. In the Decimal-Test, we expected that children would primarily produce two decimals with equal number of decimal digits for addition and subtraction. For multiplication and division, we expected that children would primarily produce a decimal and a natural number.

Task 2: Generate-operand. Children completed eight trials, each showing an empty box and a number linked by an operation (+, −, ×, ÷). In the Fraction-Test, the given number for each trial was a fraction, and children were instructed to fill the box with a fraction or a natural number. In the Decimal-Test, the given number for each trial was a decimal, and children were instructed to insert a decimal or a natural number. Unlike Task 1, where children could sometimes produce two natural numbers despite clear instructions (note that this indeed happened in the study by Braithwaite and Siegler (2018) who had to exclude 10% of trials because children produced two natural numbers), Task 2 was designed to prevent this problem. To ensure that at least one operand would be a fraction or decimal, Task 2 incorporated response formats that guide children toward valid answers.

Based on the distribution of problems in the Swiss textbooks, we made the following predictions. In the Fraction-Test, we expected that for addition and subtraction, children would primarily generate another fraction that results in a problem with two fractions with unequal denominators. For multiplication and division, we expected children to primarily generate a natural number. In the Decimal-Test, we expected children to primarily generate a decimal for addition and subtraction that results in a problem with two decimals with equal number of decimal digits; and to generate primarily a natural number for multiplication and division.

Task 3: Choose-operation. Children completed twelve trials. For each trial, they had to select an operation (+, −, ×, ÷) to insert into an empty box between two given numbers. The task in the Fraction-Test comprised four trials with equal denominators, four trials with unequal denominators, and four trials with a fraction and a natural number. The task in the Decimal-Test comprised four trials with two decimals with equal decimal digits, four trials with two decimals with unequal decimal digits, and four decimal-natural number trials.

Based on the distribution of problems in the Swiss textbooks, we made the following predictions. In the Fraction-Test, we expected that children would primarily select addition and subtraction with pairs of fractions denominators, while primarily selecting multiplication

and division with fraction–natural number pairs. In the Decimal-Test, we expected children to primarily select addition and subtraction with pairs of decimals with equal decimal digits, and to primarily select multiplication and division with decimal–natural number pairs.

Task 4: Choosing an operand pair for a given operation. Children completed twelve trials. Each trial showed an operation and two operand pairs; children had to select one pair for the given operation. The task in the Fraction-Test included (1) fractions with equal denominators vs. a natural number and a fraction, (2) fractions with unequal denominators vs. a natural number and a fraction, and (3) fractions with equal denominators vs. fractions with unequal denominators. The task in the Decimal-Test included (1) decimals with equal digits vs. a natural number and a decimal, (2) decimals with unequal digits vs. a natural number and a decimal, and (3) decimals with equal digits vs. decimals with unequal digits. The order of trials was randomized, but the order of the given operations was always $+$, $-$, \times , \div .

Based on the distribution of problems in the Swiss textbooks, we made the following predictions. In the Fraction-Test, we expected that, whenever addition or subtraction was given, children would primarily choose pairs consisting of two fractions. Conversely, we expected them to primarily choose a natural number and a fraction pair when multiplication or division was given. Similarly, in the Decimal-Test, we expected children to choose pairs of two decimals when addition or subtraction was given, and a natural number and a decimal pair when multiplication or division was given.

Task 5: Choosing an operation for given operands. Children completed twelve trials. Each trials showed a pair of operands and two pairs of boxes with an operation between each; children had to assign the operands to one operation. In the Fraction-Test, operands were either two fractions (with equal or unequal denominators) or a fraction and a natural number. For the Decimal-Test, operands were either two decimals (with equal or unequal decimal digits) or a decimal and a natural number. Task 5 complements Task 4 by reversing the decision process: while Task 4 required children to choose between operand pairs for a given operation, Task 5 required them to choose an operation for given operands. This

complementary design provides a more complete picture of how children associate numbers with operations and vice versa.

Based on the distribution of problems in the Swiss textbooks, we made the following predictions. In the Fraction-Test, we expected that children would primarily assign two fractions to the operation addition or subtraction, and a fraction and a natural number to the operation multiplication or division. In the Decimal-Test, we expected children to primarily assign two decimals to the operation addition or subtraction, and a decimal and a natural number to the operation multiplication or division.

Note that our predictions provided above were guided by the distributions of problems in Swiss textbooks. Importantly, the distribution of problems in Swiss textbooks differs to some extent from the patterns found in U.S. textbooks (Braithwaite & Siegler, 2018; Tian, Braithwaite, & Siegler, 2021). Similar to these prior studies, we predicted that children would primarily associate addition and subtraction with pairs of the same kind (fractions or decimals) and multiplication and division with mixed pairs (a natural number with a fraction or decimal). The main striking difference between Swiss and U.S. textbooks is, however, the relative frequency of equal and unequal-denominator fraction problems. Equal-denominator problems were almost entirely absent in Swiss mathematics textbooks. Thus, if Swiss children's responses to Tasks 1 and 2 in the Fraction-Test follow the specific problem distribution in Swiss textbooks (e.g., more frequently generating two fractions with unequal denominators than with equal denominators for addition and subtraction), this would support the hypothesis that the learning of spurious associations is shaped by specific patterns in mathematics textbooks rather than reflecting intrinsic characteristics of rational number arithmetic alone.

Table 3: Tasks, summary of predictions and results in the Fraction-Test.

Task 1. Generate-operands	
Instruction	Example
Write two numbers that you think would appear with +.	$\square + \square$
Prediction	Result
Children will generate two fractions with equal denominators more often for +/- than for \times/\div .	X
Children will generate two fractions with unequal denominators more often for +/- than for \times/\div .	†
Children will generate two fractions with unequal denominators more often than two fractions with equal denominators for +/-.	✓
Children will generate a fraction and a natural number more often for \times/\div than for +/-.	✓
Task 2. Generate-operand	
Instruction	Example
In the box, write a number that you think would appear with subtraction and $2/7$.	$\square - 2/7$
Prediction	Result
Children will generate a fraction more often for +/- than for \times/\div —resulting in a problem with two fractions with equal denominators.	✓
Children will generate a fraction more often for +/- than for \times/\div —resulting in a problem with two fractions with unequal denominators.	†
Children will generate +/- problems involving two fractions with unequal denominators more often than problems with equal denominators.	✓
Children will generate a natural number more often for \times/\div than for +/-.	✓
Task 3. Choose-operation	
Instruction	Example
Which arithmetic operation should appear in the box? You can choose +, -, \times , \div .	$4/5 \square 1/5$
Prediction	Result
Children will choose +/- more often than \times/\div in combination with two fractions with equal denominators.	✓
Children will choose +/- more often than \times/\div in combination with two fractions with unequal denominators	✓

Children will choose \times/\div more often than $+/-$ in combination with a fraction and a natural number.	✓
Task 4. Choosing an operand pair for a given operation	
Instruction	Example
For which problem should \times appear? You can choose:	$\frac{1}{2} \square 2$ or $\frac{2}{3} \square \frac{1}{5}$
Prediction	Result
Children will assign $+/-$ to pairs of two fractions with equal denominators more often than to a fraction–natural number pair.	✓
Children will assign $+/-$ to pairs of two fractions with unequal denominators more often than to a fraction–natural number pair.	†
Children will assign \times/\div more often than $+/-$ to the pair of operands with a fraction and a natural number.	✓
Task 5. Choosing an operation for given operands	
Instruction	Example
Should $\frac{3}{5}$ and $\frac{2}{5}$ appear in a problem with $-$ or in a problem with \times ? You can choose:	$\square - \square$ or $\square \times \square$
Prediction	Result
Children will assign fractions with equal denominators to $+/-$ more often than to \times/\div .	✓
Children will assign fractions with unequal denominators to $+/-$ more often than to \times/\div .	✓
Children will assign a fraction and a natural number to \times/\div more often than to $+/-$.	X

Note. “✓” indicates that the prediction was consistent with the result. “†” indicates that an effect exists in line with the prediction, although not reliably larger than a small effect size. “x” indicates that the prediction was not consistent with the results.

Table 4: Tasks, summary of predictions and results in the Decimal-Test.

Task 1. Generate-operands	
Instruction	Example
Write two numbers that you think would appear with $+$.	$\square + \square$
Prediction	Result
Children will generate two decimals with equal number of decimal digits more often for $+/-$ than for \times/\div .	✓

Children will generate two decimals with unequal number of decimal digits more often for $+/-$ than for \times/\div .	†
Children will generate two decimals with equal number of decimal digits more often than two decimals with unequal number of decimal digits for $+/-$.	✓
Children will generate a decimal and a natural number more often for \times/\div than for $+/-$.	✓
Task 2. Generate-operand	
Instruction	Example
In the box, write a number that you think would appear with subtraction and $2/7$.	<input type="checkbox"/> - 0.12
Prediction	Result
Children will generate a decimal more often for $+/-$ than for \times/\div —resulting in a problem with two decimals with an equal number of decimal digits.	✓
Children will generate a decimal more often for $+/-$ than for \times/\div —resulting in a problem with two decimals with an unequal number of decimal digits.	✓
Children will generate $+/-$ problems involving two decimals with an equal number of decimal digits more often than problems with an unequal number of decimal digits.	✓
Children will generate a natural number more often for \times/\div than for $+/-$.	✓
Task 3. Choose-operation	
Instruction	Example
Which arithmetic operation should appear in the box? You can choose $+$, $-$, \times , \div .	$2.5 \square 1.2$
Prediction	Result
Children will choose $+/-$ more than \times/\div in combination with two decimals with an equal number of decimal digits.	✓
Children will choose $+/-$ more than \times/\div in combination with two decimals with an unequal number of decimal digits.	✓
Children will choose \times/\div more than $+/-$ in combination with a decimal and a natural number.	✓
Task 4. Choosing an operand pair for a given operation	
Instruction	Example

For which problem should \times appear? You can choose:	1.6 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 or 1.6 <input type="checkbox"/> 0.3
Prediction	Result
Children will assign $+/-$ to pairs of two decimals with an equal number of decimal digits more often than to a decimal–natural number pair.	✓
Children will assign $+/-$ to pairs of two decimals with an unequal number of decimal digits more often than to a decimal–natural number pair.	✓
Children will assign \times/\div more than $+/-$ to the pair of operands with a decimal and a natural number.	✓
Task 5. Choosing an operation for given operands	
Instruction	Example
Should 0.08 and 0.06 appear in a problem with $-$ or in a problem with \times ? You can choose:	<input type="checkbox"/> $-$ <input type="checkbox"/> or <input type="checkbox"/> \times <input type="checkbox"/>
Prediction	Result
Children will assign two decimals with an equal number of decimal digits $+/-$ more often than to \times/\div .	✓
Children will assign two decimals with an unequal number of decimal digits $+/-$ more often than to \times/\div .	✓
Children will assign a decimal and a natural number \times/\div more often than to $+/-$.	X

Note. “✓” indicates that the prediction was consistent with the result. “+” indicates that an effect exists in line with the prediction, although not reliably larger than a small effect size. “x” indicates that the prediction was not consistent with the results.

3.1.3. Procedure

The two tests were conducted toward the end of the school year, after students had completed all instruction on fractions and decimals as defined in the compulsory Swiss curriculum (Lehrplan 21). The tests, delivered in paper-and-pencil format during regular math lessons, were supervised by the teacher, with instructions provided by the first author.

Testing lasted 90 minutes, 45 minutes per test with a short break between the two tests.

Students received a booklet per test, comprising all five tasks, with each trial printed on a separate page. In the first session, they completed the Fraction-Test; in the second session, they completed the Decimal-Test. Instructions were read aloud, and brief examples were

given before each test to activate the relevant knowledge (e.g., a reminder of what fractions, decimals or natural numbers are).

Students had 8 minutes per task and were asked to wait silently if they finished early. Each task was separated by a page saying “STOP! Please don’t turn the page” notice. The tasks followed a fixed order: from Task 1 to Task 5.

3.2. Statistical Analyses

We analysed whether students show non-random associations between operation and operand type within each task. Given that each task contained only 8 or 12 trials, overlapping/heterogeneous option sets (e.g., two superficially identical “_ + _” prompts in the Generate-operands task), and sparse cells, we modelled student-level counts rather than item-level multinomials. This approach improves identifiability and yields more stable, comparable estimates across tasks.

Specifically, for each child and task, we computed the number of trials for each combination of operation and operand type and modelled these counts out of the student’s total opportunities for that combination within that task. For both the Fraction- and the Decimal-Tests, we required at least 75% valid responses per child and task for inclusion. This ensured <1.6% invalid trials per task while maintaining adequate sample sizes. These counts were modelled with binomial mixed models with *brms* (Bürkner, 2018), accounting for the repeated measurement by specifying a random effect for students. The specific analyses, however, depended on the task and the specific predictions for it.

For tasks 1, 2 and 4, we tested the association between operation and operand type by comparing the baseline model with only main effects for operation and operand type to a model including their interaction, using the same maximal random-effects structure (Barr, Levy, Scheepers, & Tily, 2013). If the interaction model fitted better, we compared operations within each operand type to examine the association. Additionally, for Tasks 1 and 2 in the Fraction-Test, we compared the probabilities of fraction pairs with unequal and equal

denominators for +/-, and in the Decimal-Test, we compared the probabilities of decimal pairs with equal and unequal number of decimal digits for +/-, to test whether children's associations mirror the distinctive pattern observed in Swiss textbooks (as opposed to U.S. textbooks). For Tasks 3 and 5, where each trial was designed to be either +/- or */+ (forced choice), we modeled counts for +/- by operand type only to avoid collinearity during estimation, and compared a model with a random slope for operand type to a baseline without it. In this case, PD is the percentage of the posterior above (or below) 0.5 on the probability scale and the ROPE (for a small effect) is a predefined range of roughly 0.455 – 0.545 in probability.

Across all regression analyses, we used the same dummy coding as in Study 1 for operation and operand type. We used the same priors, adding Cholesky factors ($\eta = 2$) for the student random effects. We again ran 4 chains with 5,000 iterations (1,000 warm-up) and compared models via LOO cross-validation ($\Delta\text{elpd}_{\text{loo}}$; Vehtari, Gelman, & Gabry, 2017).

Finally, to better understand interindividual variation and unexpected results, we performed exploratory analyses to group students using K-means clustering (Hartigan-Wong algorithm, 100 random starts). For each task, we ran a separate cluster analysis using the counts by operation and operand type for each student as the input. The number of clusters for each task was determined by identifying the "elbow" in a plot of variance reduction versus number of clusters. This method suggested 3 clusters for 8 out of 10 tasks (across Fraction and Decimal Tests) and 4 clusters for the remaining two tasks (Task 3: Choose-operation in the Fraction-Test and Task 2: Generate-operand in the Decimal-Test). We choose to estimate 3 clusters for all tasks to ensure consistency and comparability across tasks and sufficient cluster sample sizes.

3.3. Results

3.3.1. Results: Fraction-Test

Table 5 shows children's responses in the Fraction-Test across the five tasks as percentages. Figure 2 illustrates the response distribution across tasks by operand type,

contrasting +/- with x/÷. The left side of this figure shows regression analysis results; the right side presents the exploratory cluster findings per task. See Table 3 for an overview of our predictions and results for each task. Below, we detail the Fraction-Test results for each task.

Task 1: Generate-operands. Data from 19 children were excluded due to providing fewer than 75% valid responses, leaving 86 children with only 1.6% missing responses. The interaction model fitted the data better than the baseline model ($\Delta\text{elpd}_{\text{loo}} = -99.3$, $\Delta\text{SE} = 13.7$). For the operand type equal denominators, the contrast of +/- vs. x/÷ had an 83.70% probability of being positive (Median = 0.03, 89% CI [-0.02, 0.07]), in line with our expectation, is not significant (20.31% in ROPE). For the operand type unequal denominators, the contrast of +/- vs. x/÷ had a 99.15% probability of being positive (Median = 0.13, 89% CI [0.04, 0.22]), aligning with our expectation, though not significant (4.17% in ROPE). However, for fraction-natural number operands, the contrast had a 100% probability of being negative (Median = -0.24, 89% CI [-0.32, -0.15]), which was significant as expected (0.02% in ROPE). This suggests that children tend to generate two fractions with unequal denominators in combination with +/- and primarily generate a fraction-natural number pair in combination with x/÷. Moreover, as predicted, children generated more frequently unequal denominator pairs than equal denominator pairs when presented with +/- (Median = 0.27, 89% CI [0.16, 0.38], PD = 99.99%, 0.01% in ROPE).

Cluster analysis showed three subgroups: Children in Cluster 1 (N=37) showed the predicted pattern, while Cluster 2 (N=30) and Cluster 3 (N=19) deviated. Children in Cluster 2 generated more fractions and whole numbers with both x/÷ and +/-, and Cluster 3 more often two fractions (particularly unequal denominators) with both x/÷ and +/-.

Task 2: Generate-operand. Data from 4 children were excluded, leaving 101 children with only 1.4% missing responses. The interaction model fitted the data better than the baseline model ($\Delta\text{elpd}_{\text{loo}} = -185.0$, $\Delta\text{SE} = 18.4$). For equal denominators, the contrast of +/- vs. x/÷ had a 100% probability of being positive (Median = 0.10, 89% CI [0.06, 0.14]) and was

significant (0.01% in ROPE). For unequal denominators, the contrast had a 98.46% probability of being positive (Median = 0.13, 89% CI [0.04, 0.22]), aligning with the direction of our prediction, however, statistically not significant (5.58% in ROPE). For fraction-natural number operands, the contrast had a 100% probability of being negative (Median = -0.30, 89% CI [-0.40, -0.21]) and was significant (0.01% in ROPE). Similar to Task 1, this suggests that children have the strong tendency to associate a fraction to the operations $+/-$ and a natural number to the operations \times/\div . Moreover, as predicted, children generated more frequently unequal denominator pairs than equal denominator pairs when presented with $+/-$ (Median = 0.24, 89% CI [0.15, 0.34], PD = 100%, 0.01% in ROPE).

Cluster analysis showed that children in Cluster 1 (N=50) followed the predicted pattern, while children in Cluster 2 (N=28) generated more often fractions and whole numbers with both $+/-$ and \times/\div , and children in Cluster 3 (N=23) generated two fractions with unequal denominators with both with $+/-$ and \times/\div .

Task 3: Choose-operation. Data from all 105 participants were included with 0.6% missing responses. The interaction model fitted the data better than the baseline model ($\Delta\text{elpd}_{\text{loo}} = -2.5$, $\Delta\text{SE} = 2.1$). For equal denominators, the probability for the choice of $+/-$ was 100% larger than 0.5 (Median = 0.67, 89% CI [0.63, 0.71]). This effect was significant (0.00% in ROPE), indicating that $+/-$ was more likely to be chosen than \times/\div , as predicted. A similar pattern of results was found for unequal denominators (Median = 0.74, 89% CI [0.70, 0.78], PD = 100%, significant at 0.00% in ROPE). For fraction-natural number operands, the probability for the choice of $+/-$ was 100% smaller than 0.5 (Median = 0.36, 89% CI [0.32, 0.40], significant at 0.01% in ROPE).

Cluster analysis showed that children in Cluster 1 (n = 54) followed the expected pattern, while children in Clusters 2 (N=30) and 3 (N=21) partially deviated, though overall regression results aligned with our predictions.

Task 4: Choosing an operand pair for a given operation. Data from all 105 participants were included, with 0.6% missing responses. The interaction model fitted the data better than the baseline model ($\Delta\text{elpd}_{\text{loo}} = -238.6$, $\Delta\text{SE} = 19.5$). For the equal denominator operands, the contrast of $+/-$ vs. \times/\div had a 99.91% probability of being positive (Median = 0.22, 89% CI [0.11, 0.34]) and was significant (0.65% in ROPE). For unequal denominators, the contrast had a 91.47% probability of being positive (Median = 0.08, 89% CI [-0.01, 0.18]), but while a tendency in direction of our expectation exists, it was not significant (25.00% in ROPE). For fraction-natural number operands, the contrast had a 99.99% probability of being negative (Median = -0.19, 89% CI [-0.27, -0.11]) and, as expected, was significant (0.16% in ROPE).

Cluster analysis showed that children in Cluster 1 (N=26) followed the predicted pattern, while children in Clusters 2 (N=50) and 3 (N=29) partially deviated, with children in Cluster 2 assigning the operation more often to two fractions and in Cluster 3 to a fraction and a natural number.

Task 5: Choosing an operation for given operands. Data from all 105 participants were included, with 1.2% missing responses. The interaction model fitted the data better than the baseline model ($\Delta\text{elpd}_{\text{loo}} = -80.0$, $\Delta\text{SE} = 13.7$). For the equal denominator operands, the probability for the choice of $+/-$ was 100% larger than 0.5 (Median = 0.91, 89% CI [0.86, 0.95]). This effect was significant (0.00% in ROPE), as expected. The same holds for unequal denominators (Median = 0.85, 89% CI [0.80, 0.89], significant at 0.00% in ROPE). However, for fraction-natural number operands, the probability for the choice of $+/-$ was 92.90% larger than 0.5 (Median = 0.57, 89% CI [0.49, 0.65]) and was not significant (27.68% in ROPE). Children tended to assign the given operands to $+/-$ rather than \times/\div , possibly basing their decision simply on the first operation being presented in the trial.

Cluster analysis showed that children in Cluster 1 (N=29) followed the predicted pattern, while children in Clusters 2 (N=27) and 3 (N=49) partially deviated. Children in Cluster 2 assigned more often two fractions with unequal denominators or fractions and whole

numbers to +/- . In Cluster 3, children assigned operands more often to +/- regardless of operand type.

Table 5: Percentage of children's responses for the Fraction-Test classified by operand types and arithmetic operations for the five tasks

Operand types per task	Operations	
	+/-	×/÷
Task 1. Generate-operands		
Equal denominators	19	11
Unequal denominators	40	31
Fraction-natural number	41	58
Task 2. Generate-operand		
Equal denominators	21	8
Unequal denominators	42	33
Fraction-natural number	37	59
Task 3. Choose-operation		
Equal denominators	66	34
Unequal denominators	74	26
Fraction-natural number	36	64
Task 4. Choosing an operand pair for a given operation		
Equal denominators	59	43
Unequal denominators	51	44
Fraction-natural number	40	57
Task 5. Choosing an operation for given operands		
Equal denominators	85	15
Unequal denominators	81	19
Fraction-natural number	54	46

Figure 2: Distribution of responses for the five tasks in the Fraction-Test presented by the three groups of operands and contrasted for +/- vs. \times/\div . In Tasks 3 and 5, \times/\div values were computed by subtracting their estimates from 100. Left side: Results of the regression analysis. Estimated median values for the whole sample are depicted as black symbols and 89% credible intervals as error bars (McElreath, 2020). Effects considered to be significant are highlighted by asterisks. Right side: Results of the exploratory cluster analysis. Observed mean values for the three clusters are depicted as well as the corresponding sample sizes.

3.3.2. Results: Decimal-Test

Table 6 shows children's responses in the Decimal-Test, classified by operand types and arithmetic operations across the five tasks as percentages. Figure 3 illustrates the response distribution for the tasks by operand groups, contrasting +/- with */+. The left side of the figure shows regression analysis results; the right side presents the cluster analysis results. See Table 4 for an overview of our predictions and results for each task for the Decimal-Test. Below, we detail the Decimal-Test results for each task.

Task 1: Generate-operands. Data from 45 children were excluded due to providing fewer than 75% valid responses or generating natural numbers for both operands. Among the remaining 60 children, 1.0% of responses were missing. The interaction model fitted the data better than the baseline model ($\Delta\text{elpd}_{\text{loo}} = -220.2$, $\Delta\text{SE} = 20.8$). For operands with an equal number of decimal digits, the contrast of +/- vs. */+ was 100% positive (Median = 0.53, 89% CI [0.41, 0.66]) and, as predicted, was significant (0.00% in ROPE), in line with our expectation. For unequal decimal digits, the contrast was 92.96% positive (Median = 0.02, 89% CI [-0.01, 0.05]), and not significant (8.68% in ROPE). For decimal-natural number operands, the contrast was 100% negative (Median = -0.53, 89% CI [-0.62, -0.43]) and significant (0.00% in ROPE), as expected. Moreover, as predicted, children generated more frequently decimal pairs with equal than unequal number of decimal digits when presented with +/- (Median = 0.64, 89% CI [0.50, 0.76], PD = 100%, 0.00% in ROPE).

Cluster analysis showed that children in all clusters rarely generated two decimals with unequal digits for either operation. In Cluster 2 (N=20), they generated more often a decimal and a natural number. In Clusters 1 (N=26) and 3 (N=14) they generated more often two decimals with equal digits.

Task 2: Generate-operand. Data from 2 children were excluded, leaving 103 participants with 0.5% missing responses. The interaction model fitted the data better than the baseline model ($\Delta\text{elpd}_{\text{loo}} = -165.3$, $\Delta\text{SE} = 15.7$). For operands with equal decimal digits, the contrast of +/- vs. */+ was 99.98% positive (Median = 0.20, 89% CI [0.10, 0.28]) and significant

(0.19% in ROPE), as expected. For unequal decimal digits, the contrast was 99.94% positive (Median = 0.09, 89% CI [0.04, 0.13]) and was significant (0.61% in ROPE), too. Also, in line with our expectation, for decimal-natural number operands, the contrast was 100% negative (Median = -0.34, 89% CI [-0.41, -0.27]) and significant (0.00% in ROPE). Moreover, as predicted, children generated more frequently decimal pairs with equal number of decimal digits than pairs with unequal number of decimal digits when presented with +/- (Median = 0.27, 89% CI [0.17, 0.36], PD = 100%, 0.00% in ROPE).

Overall, these results supported our expectations. Cluster analysis showed that children in Cluster 1 (N=51) aligned with our predictions. Clusters 2 (N=28) and 3 (N=24) partially deviated with children in Cluster 2 generating more often a decimal and a natural number, and children in Cluster 3 showing no specific pattern.

Task 3: Choose-operation. Data from all 105 participants were analyzed, with 0.4% missing responses. The interaction model fitted the data better than the baseline model ($\Delta\text{elpd}_{\text{loo}} = -9.1$, $\Delta\text{SE} = 3.8$). For operands with equal decimal digits, the probability for the choice of +/- was 100% larger than 0.5 (Median = 0.65, 89% CI [0.61, 0.69]) and significant (0.01% in ROPE), as expected. The same holds true for unequal decimal digits (Median = 0.70, 89% CI [0.65, 0.75], PD = 100%, 0.00% in ROPE). For decimal-natural number operands, probability for the choice of +/- was 100% smaller than 0.5 (Median = 0.34, 89% CI [0.30, 0.38], 0.00% in ROPE). Overall, the regression results supported predictions.

Cluster analysis also showed that children in Cluster 1 (N=48) aligned with predictions, while children in Clusters 2 (N=19) and 3 (N=38) did not show the expected pattern.

Task 4: Choosing an operand pair for a given operation. Data from 2 children were excluded, leaving 103 participants with 0.2% missing responses. The interaction model fitted the data better than the baseline model ($\Delta\text{elpd}_{\text{loo}} = -159.8$, $\Delta\text{SE} = 15.3$). For operands with equal decimal digits, the contrast of +/- vs. \times/\div was 100% positive (Median = 0.22, 89% CI [0.14, 0.30]) and significant (0.03% in ROPE), as expected. For unequal decimal digits

(Median = 0.20, 89% CI [0.11, 0.29], 0.47% in ROPE), the contrast was 99.92% positive and significant. For decimal-natural number operands, the contrast was 100% negative (Median = -0.21, 89% CI [-0.29, -0.14], 0.03% in ROPE) and significant, as expected. Overall, these results supported our predictions.

Cluster analysis showed that children in Cluster 1 (N=41) aligned with our predictions.

Children in Clusters 2 (N=36) and 3 (N=26) partially contradicted them: there was no clear pattern in Cluster 2, and children in Cluster 3 more often assigned operations to a decimal and a natural number.

Task 5: Choosing an operation for given operands. Data from 3 children were excluded, leaving 102 participants with 1.2% missing responses. The interaction model fitted the data to a similar degree than the baseline model ($\Delta\text{elp}_{\text{loo}} = -1.7$, $\Delta\text{SE} = 1.7$), but for comparability across tasks, the contrasts were computed as done for the other tasks. For operands with equal decimal digits, the probability for the choice of +/- was 100% larger than 0.5 (Median = 0.83, 89% CI [0.80, 0.87]) and significant (0.00% in ROPE). Similarly, for unequal decimal digits (Median = 0.91, 89% CI [0.85, 0.96]), the contrast was 100% positive and significant. For decimal-natural numbers, the contrast was also 100% positive (Median = 0.66, 89% CI [0.61, 0.71], 0.07% in ROPE) but contradicted predictions, suggesting a preference for +/- regardless of operand type, making findings for this task less reliable.

Cluster analysis showed that children in Cluster 1 (N=43) aligned with our predictions, in Cluster 2 (N=13) they displayed an inverse pattern, and in Cluster 3 (N=46) they assigned operands to +/- which was typically the first operation presented.

Table 6: Percentage of children's responses for the Decimal-Test classified by operand types and arithmetic operations for the five tasks

Operand types per task	Operations	
	+/-	×/÷
Task 1. Generate-operands		
Equal number of decimal digits	64	25
Unequal number of decimal digits	9	3
Decimal-natural number	28	72
Task 2. Generate-operand		
Equal number of decimal digits	46	30
Unequal number of decimal digits	21	10
Decimal-natural number	33	61
Task 3. Choose-operation		
Equal number of decimal digits	65	35
Unequal number of decimal digits	67	33
Decimal-natural number	34	66
Task 4. Choosing an operand pair for a given operation		
Equal number of decimal digits	59	40
Unequal number of decimal digits	40	29
Decimal-natural number	44	64
Task 5. Choosing an operation for given operands		
Equal number of decimal digits	79	21
Unequal number of decimal digits	87	13
Decimal-natural number	63	37

Figure 3: Distribution of responses for the five tasks in the Decimal-Test presented by the three groups of operands and contrasted for +/-vs. In Tasks 3 and 5, \times/\div . \times/\div values were computed by subtracting their estimates from 100. Left side: Results of the regression analysis. Estimated median values for the whole sample are depicted as black symbols and 89% credible intervals as error bars (McElreath, 2020). Effects considered to be significant are highlighted by asterisks. Right side: Results of the exploratory cluster analysis. Observed mean values for the three clusters are depicted as well as the corresponding sample sizes.

4. Discussion

We examined the distributions of rational arithmetic problems in two widely used mathematics textbooks in Swiss German primary schools (Study 1) and investigated whether children learned spurious associations based on the distributions (Study 2). Conceptually replicating Braithwaite and Siegler (2018) and Tian et al. (2022) findings obtained in the U.S., we used their tasks and designed two additional tasks to capture a broader range of responses. By modelling Bayesian binomial regressions and conducting exploratory cluster analyses, we accounted for sample variability, offering nuanced analyses of task distributions and children's performance.

In Study 1, consistent with Braithwaite and Siegler's (2018) and Tian et al.'s (2021), we identified non-random patterns of how rational number problems are designed in textbooks. Fraction problems often paired addition (+)/subtraction (-) with unequal denominators and multiplication (\times)/division (\div) with fractions and natural numbers. Decimal problems often paired +/- with two decimals with equal digits and \times/\div with a decimal and a natural number.

Study 1 revealed clear nonrandom and unbalanced relations between arithmetic operations and operand features in both textbooks, differing slightly from the patterns observed by Braithwaite and Siegler (2018). Specifically, Swiss textbooks include far fewer fraction problems with equal denominators (in both books, SZB and MTB, around 5%). Instead, most addition and subtraction problems involve fractions with unequal denominators (56% in SZB and 23% in MTB). However, similar to Braithwaite and Siegler (2018), most fraction-natural number problems involved multiplication and division (26% in SZB and 68% in MTB).

The analyses of decimal arithmetic problems in Swiss textbooks match Tian et al.'s findings (2021) for U.S textbooks (see also Table 2), showing a nonrandom and unbalanced distribution, too. For instance, in SZB only 12% and in MTB only 16% of addition and subtraction problems involve decimals with unequal decimal digits, while 32% in SZB and 34% in MTB involve decimals with equal decimal digits. Moreover, multiplication and division

problems between two decimals are rare (only 5% in SZB and 0.0% in MTB), with most problems (37% in SZB, 46% in MTB) involving a natural number and a decimal.

Study 2 showed that Swiss children learned spurious associations from the non-random patterns of rational number arithmetic problems in textbooks. We begin the description of our findings with the Fraction-Test. When asked to generate operand(s) (Tasks 1 & 2), children had the tendency to pair \pm with two fractions with unequal denominators and \times/\div with fraction-natural number pairs. With Tasks 1 and 2, we further could test whether a specific pattern found in Swiss textbooks, but not in U.S. textbooks, has an impact on children. More precisely, in Swiss textbooks the operations \pm are more frequently presented with fractions involving unequal rather than equal denominators. Consistent with this pattern, children's behavior mirrored this pattern: they generated more unequal denominator pairs of fractions than equal denominator pairs in combination with \pm . When having to choose an operation (Task 3), children preferred \pm for two fractions and \times/\div for fraction-natural number pairs. When asked to choose an operand pair for a given operation (Task 4), children tended to assign \pm to two fractions and \times/\div to fraction-natural number pairs. Similar behavior emerged when asked to assign an operation to given operands (Task 5), however with the unexpected finding that children occasionally favored \pm for mixed pairs of operands. In sum, children tended to associate multiplication and division with fraction–natural number combinations and addition and subtraction with two fractions, regardless of denominators. Occasionally, unequal-denominator fractions were also linked to multiplication or division. While children's responses largely reflected textbook patterns, these unexpected observations point to fruitful directions for future research. Overall, these results complement the findings of Braithwaite and Siegler (2018), suggesting that children learn spurious association from their textbook fraction arithmetic problem distributions.

In the Decimal-Test, when asked to generate operand(s) (Tasks 1 & 2), combinations with equal-digit decimals for \pm and decimal-natural number for \times/\div were observed. In Swiss textbooks the operations \pm are more frequently presented with two decimals with an equal

number of decimal digits than with an unequal number of decimal digits. Children's behavior mirrored this pattern: they generated more decimals with equal number of decimal digits than with unequal number of decimals digits when presented with $+/-$. When having to choose an operation (Task 3), $+/-$ was favored for two decimals and \times/\div for decimal-natural number pairs. When asked to choose an operand pair for a given operation (Task 4), similar patterns emerged. Finally, when asked to assign an operation to given operands (Task 5), children more often paired decimals pairs (equal or unequal digits) and decimal-natural number pairs with $+/-$ than with \times/\div . This unexpected finding was also observed for responses to the corresponding task in the Fraction-Test. Closer inspection of this unexpected finding for Task 5 in both tests revealed that many children ignored the operands and simply selected the first given operation (see Tables 3 and 4 for example trials of Task 5). Nevertheless, the overall results across the tasks align with the pattern in the textbooks, indicating that children learn spurious association from their textbook decimal arithmetic problem distributions.

Cluster analyses for each task in both tests revealed distinct patterns in how children approached the tasks. There was always one cluster (typically the largest share of children) which answered as predicted, that is, consistently favoring specific operations or operand combinations. Two other clusters showed less systematic biases deviating from our predictions and varying in their deviations across tasks. This exploratory analysis refines the overall findings, showing that some children closely follow textbook patterns, while others are less influenced. These findings are consistent with prior work highlighting individual differences in children's strategy use and fraction arithmetic performance, including the role of global biases, relevant and irrelevant feature effects in strategy choice (Braithwaite & Rafferty, 2025), as well as distinct performance patterns predicted by computational models of fraction arithmetic (Braithwaite, Leib, Siegler, & McMullen, 2019). Note that for decimal arithmetic (in contrast to fraction arithmetic; see next paragraph), no prior studies with children from other countries were available to compare with the Swiss children's response patterns. Therefore, additional research in other countries is needed to determine whether

these patterns reflect inherent aspects of decimal number arithmetic or are the result of associative learning.

The finding that the fraction problem distributions in Swiss textbooks partly diverge from U.S. patterns (as identified by Braithwaite & Siegler) provides an additional opportunity to evaluate the associative learning hypothesis. Given that most Swiss children's responses in the Fraction-Test of Study 2 reflected specific patterns in their Swiss textbooks—differing from the patterns identified in U.S. mathematics textbooks—supports the associative learning hypothesis. Specifically, in Tasks 1 and 2, when Swiss children saw the operation $+/-$, they produced more often two fractions with unequal denominators rather than with equal denominators. This specific unbalanced presentation of tasks in Swiss textbook is not present in U.S. textbooks and was not found in U.S. children's associations. Thus, our results provide additional empirical support that associations of children reflect their textbook task pattern rather than inherent features of fraction arithmetic. At the same time, the cluster analyses qualify this finding for the whole sample: not all children learned spurious associations from their textbooks. Scrutinizing the origins of these interindividual differences is an important direction for future research. The assessment of additional individual cognitive and motivational characteristics of children are necessary to improve our understanding of what makes children resilient to learning spurious associations from their textbooks.

4.1. Limitations

We replicated and extended prior studies using nuanced statistical analyses to characterize problem distributions in textbooks and to assess children's associations between operations and operand features in rational number arithmetic. While our findings suggest that problem distributions lead (some) children to form spurious associations, several limitations must be considered.

First, our findings are correlational. While we observed non-random distributions between operations and operands in Swiss textbooks, we cannot claim a causal link to children's

performance. As Braithwaite and Siegler (2018) highlighted, U.S. learn spurious associations from their textbooks. Additionally, they also investigated Chinese textbooks which showed non-random distributions of tasks, too. However, Chinese children and seem not to learn spurious associations to a similar extent as U.S. children. According to our explorative cluster analyses, not all children learn associations based on textbook distributions. Maybe some children learned with additional resources provided by their teachers or trained with additional materials at home. Future research needs to focus on these individual differences.

Second, while our cluster analysis offers an initial exploration into grouping children based on their responses parallel to textbook patterns, we did not collect additional individual characteristics that could provide insights on what predicts membership in a cluster. Factors like working memory, motivation, and learning strategies could further elucidate each cluster's characteristics. Our analysis, indicating that not all children learn spurious associations, should be considered a preliminary step.

Third, following Braithwaite and Siegler (2018) and Tian et al. (2021), we only analyzed symbolic numerical arithmetic problems. However, students also encounter other problem formats in their textbooks (e.g., word problems) and they may also receive problems designed by their teachers. Tian et al. (2022) suggest that teachers may unintentionally mirror textbooks biases, however direct evidence for this suggestion is still lacking. Therefore, further research is needed that takes various problem formats and potential additional learning opportunities into account.

4.2. Conclusion

Prior research suggests that biased distributions of rational number problems in textbooks can impede arithmetic competence because children learn spurious associations from their textbook problems (Braithwaite et al., 2017; Braithwaite & Siegler, 2018; Son & Senk, 2010; Tian et al., 2021). A potential solution is to design textbook with a balanced problem distribution using random combinations of operands and operators. Future studies should examine whether this approach improves arithmetic skills. Currently, our findings, along with

prior research, highlight the risk of children forming spurious associations due to non-random problem distributions. Teachers and textbook designers need to be aware of this issue and aim for balanced distribution and presentations of arithmetic problems in their instruction.

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